

Drug addiction, a consequence of ills rather than individual flaws

The spread of multiple drug use has aggravated the overall problem, personal and social impairment of health, crime and other violent behaviours

ABDUL KADER MOHIUDDIN

Addiction is a maladaptive pattern of drug abuse including alcohol, caffeine, cannabis, hallucinogens, inhalants, opioids, sedatives, hypnotics and anxiolytics, stimulants, tobacco and others that persist despite negative consequences. An article of New England Journal of Medicine says "addiction is a disease of the brain" whereas another leading journal specifies: "Genetics contributes significantly to vulnerability to this disorder". Neurological changes observed in long-term substance abusers are nearly identical to those seen in people struggling with obesity, porn aficionados, gamblers, internet "addicts", compulsive shoppers and simply those involved in intense romantic relationships. As with many other brain diseases, addiction has embedded behavioural and social-context aspects that are important parts of the disorder itself.

Globally, 50% of deaths of liver cirrhosis, 30% of deaths of oral and pharyngeal cancers, 22% of deaths of interpersonal violence, 22% of deaths of suicide, 15% of deaths of traffic injuries, 12% of deaths of tuberculosis, and 12% of deaths of liver cancer were attributed to alcohol consumption, according to Journal of Family Medicine and Primary Care, 2019. The WHO estimated that there are 2 billion alcohol users, 1.3 billion tobacco users, and 185 million illicit-drug users worldwide. Currently, 80% of tobacco users live in low- and middle-income countries. Smoking and alcohol abuse collectively made India a home of 277 million

where 30% fatal car crashes are "drunk and drive" cases. The prevalence of alcohol use disorder is highest in Europe (7.5%) and the lowest among East Mediterranean Regions which includes Afghanistan, Bahrain, and Egypt. In the US, the largest national economy of the world, 75% of high-school students have reportedly used illegal drugs, drunk alcohol or smoked tobacco, and opioids claim 40,000 death each year from overdose.

Bangladesh is situated in the crucial point between the 'golden triangle' (Myanmar, Thailand and Laos) and the 'golden crescent' (Pakistan, Afghanistan and Iran) in terms of geographical location. Bangladesh with its easy land, sea, and air access is becoming a major transit point. Traffickers who supply drugs in the markets of Northern America, Africa, and Europe are routing their shipments through Dhaka, Chittagong, Comilla, Khulna and other routes in Bangladesh. It ultimately contributes to the number of drug abusers as well. The

33% of abusers started between 15-19 years old. A study conducted in the outpatient department of National Institute of Mental Health in Dhaka, revealed that 7.66% of respondents suffered from a substance-related disorder. A similar study conducted in a private psychiatric clinic in Dhaka showed that around 30% of admitted psychiatric patients were suffering from substance-related disorder. Meanwhile, a separate study conducted by ICDDR, B shows that in the capital, around 80% of the users are male and 20% are female.

Despite prohibition, alcohol is available across the country and is produced locally. Locally produced alcoholic beverages are made from sorghum, maize, millet, rice, cider, fruit wine or fortified wine (tari, bangla mod, haria, choani, ek chuani, do chuani, mohua, etc.). Data from the HIV behavioural surveillance survey conducted in 2016 among people who inject drugs (PWID) in Dhaka city showed that 53.1% of PWID shared needles and

among this segment of population over the past decade despite the ongoing Needle and Syringe Programme (NSP).

It is estimated that there were about 4.6 million regular users of Yaba (several combinations of N-methylamphetamine and caffeine sold within BDT 300 to BDT 2000, as red or pink pills) in Bangladesh on or before 2012, which is around 10-15 million, according to Association of Prohibiting Drug Abuse (MANAS) chief Dr. Arup Ratan Chaudhury. Around 80% of drug abusers are young people aged between 16 and 35, said the Department of Narcotic Control report, 2016 by the Home Ministry. A BBC report April, 2019 says that Bangladeshi authorities seized 53 million Yaba tablets nationally in 2018. The total value of this illicit business is estimated to be worth upwards of \$1 billion a year. Over half of the public vehicle drivers take drugs regularly and it could be the main reason for accidents in the country.

The spread of multiple drug use

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